

Myths and Legends related to the Origin and Construction of Surya Deula, Konark

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: May

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3335904>

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Abstract

Myths and legends are part of a land's culture. In South Asia, especially any place, mountain, river, rocks, cities, things or matter is divinely associated with a story. Our scriptures are replete with these tales and stories of religion. The most important of these legends are the medico connection with the belief that the light of the sun is a cure for leprosy. Three great names associate with the worship of the sun god. Samba, son of lord Krishna, Mayur, Celebrated poet of king Harshavardhana and the Ganga king Narasingha-I. All three seems to have suffered from leprosy. Two of them are directly associated with the monument of Konark; Samba and its builder in myth and legend and Narasingha in history. The current paper deals with the Myths and Legends related and how these literary evidences from Puranas and Contemporary manuscripts leads to the better understanding of the Origin and Construction of Surya Deula temple at Konark, Orissa, India.

Introduction

The state of Orissa (separated from Bihar in CE., 1936), extends from 17°49' - North to 22°34' North latitude and from 81°29' east to 87°29' East longitude on the eastern coast of India. It has an extremely rich cultural heritage. Known as Kalinga in ancient times, throughout its long history, numerous divisions of the land divide the country. Hiuen-Tsang (Yuwan Chwang) visited Orissa in the 7th Century CE. Three distinct regions divided the state with the name Kalinga applied to the southernmost area that apparently extended from the southern portions of modern Ganjam district to the river Godavari in Andhra Pradesh. Kongada was the name of the area North to Kalinga, which extended up to Chilka Lake. Odra was the Northern portion of Orissa. Kongada formed part of South Tosali, the latter extended to the Mahanadi river while, the area north of this centrally located river was called North Tosali and extended up to the Vaitarani river.

During the Ganga period the most ambitious project undertaken and one of the most breathtaking projects ever attempted in India,

was the construction of the Surya temple at Konark (Lat.19.35°N, long.86°E) (Figure 1). Narasimha I (A.D 1238-1264) spearheaded the project at Konark. He was still a crown prince when the work started (Baya Cakada, leaf iii, 9). Records in Baya Cakada also mention that Narasimha recruited more than 500 workers for the construction of the temple. Warangal campaign witnessed the joining of the temple construction workers with the king. It was not of free will but an order by the king. This was a second campaign in South, which took place in the 4th year after his coronation.

The same manuscript also mentions although building operations started in the 5th Anka of his reign, planning and quarrying of stones had begun some six years earlier.

Abul-Fazil's *Ain-i-Akbari* (CE., 1581) has it that the revenue for 12 years from the entire country was defrayed for the construction of that 12,000 men toiled ceaselessly and laboriously on the work, often despondent, often frustrated, by the immense difficulty of the task, (H.S. Jarrett and Jadu-nath Sarkar, 1949. : 140-141) (Thomas. E. Donaldson, 1986: 592-593).

Myths and Legends

Myths and legends are part of a land's culture. In India, especially any place, mountain, river, rocks, cities, things or matter is divinely associated with a story. Our scriptures are replete with these tales and stories of religion. The most important of these legends are the medico connection with the belief that the light of the sun is a cure for leprosy. Three great names associate with the worship of the sun god. On this account Samba, son of lord Krishna, Mayur, Celebrated poet of king Harshavardhana and the Ganga king Narasingha-I. Mayur the poet having been cured of this dire disease through the favour of this deity composed a great poem of hundred stanzas in praise of the sun. All three seems to have suffered from leprosy. Two of them are directly associated with the monument of Konark; Samba and its builder in myth and legend and Narasingha in history.

The great period of sun worship, influenced by the Maga priests from Iran, slowly spread from the west to the east of India. The Sumandala copperplate inscription of 599 CE., contains the earliest historical evidence of sun worship in Orissa of one Maharaja Dharmaraja. The Maharaja mentions that he descended from Raja Abhaya of Padma Kholya and calls himself a devotee at the feet of the thousand rayed.

Yet the worship of the sun god in India was certainly more ancient still and can as in the rest of India, be traced back to the Vedas. Rig Veda- (I .164) attributes to Dirghatamas, the blind seer, considered a kind of missionary of the Arya faith in Orissa. This hymn one of the most difficult of the entire Rig Veda gives a profound interpretation of sun symbolism; Surya with his brothers Agni and Vayu is at the source of all creation cosmic and spiritual. The chariot of Surya Deva is the symbol of the cosmos as well as of the human organism. He himself is the charioteer. The wheel in movement symbolises time. One single wheel signifies time absolute and truth absolute, the unity underlying all manifestation. The wheel said to be in seven fold, symbolizes the splitting up of that unity into created manifestation. Similarly, the seven horses, the seven rays, seven colours, the seven notes, seven metres, seven Rishis or Puranic forces all refer to the various fundamental energies emerging from the primal undifferentiated unity. Surya is also the great horse, the time horse, even on the more immortal. The three naves symbolize the triple nature of manifestation; spirit, life and matter, the three Devas or Pranas, the three Vedas, the three seasons by which the cycle of the year is maintained, the three aspects of time, the absolute, the differentiated and the concrete time of the material world. Again, spokes of the wheel of time, which never decay are the twelve months of the year (Samvatsara). The twelve constellations (Nakshatra) with 720 sons of Surya joined in pairs of 360 days and nights are the revolving movement of the great wheel. This wheel, as the principle of movement is the support of the countless worlds. The horses yoked to the chariot are the dynamic time principle at the origin of movement, which itself governed by

a timeless, ageless, ordinance (Boner, Sharma and Das: XXXIII). All these ideologies leads one towards the understanding of the life cycle may be it of man or nature.

Doctrine and symbolism of the sun god's iconographic representation in Orissa belong to the second period of sun worship under the influence of the Magas from Iran. Finally, the tantric doctrines were responsible for much of the later forms of iconic and symbolic worship and imagery of sun god.

The Samba Purana narrates the story of Samba. This very legend provides the base for the second phase of sun worship. From there it has passed with many variations to other Puranas such as Bhavishya, the Varaha, the Skanda Puranas. The versions differ. Two different sections of the Samba Purana give two main versions of the story widely apart in space and time. One locates the legend in the north-west India, in the Punjab; the second locates it on the eastern ocean in Orissa.

The Samba Purana (Kanwar Lal 1967: 9) gives a detailed account of the mythical episode. The location of the first act of the drama is at Dwaraka during the golden age of Krishna's rule. Before Dvapara Yuga, it was through tough penance that mortal has attained Moksha. Krishna the Dvarakadisha wanted men and women to live not through the philosophy of penance and self-mortification, but to follow the easy and the natural course of fulfilling their desires. He wanted an easier path and advised that love was the path to liberation. Delight of the senses would make one. Singing one's way in the path of love and affection, one could almost attain Nirvan, the liberation.

Samba was a handsome son of Krishna. Narada muni always comes to this world with his tricky ideals for the upliftment of the human kind. Narada's scheme, accused Samba before his father (Krishna) of having tried seducing his wives. The incensed Krishna therefore cursed him to become a leper. The Bhavishya Purana gives another account that Samba son of Sri Krishna and Jambavati. Rishi Durvasa cursed him to become a leper due to his ill deeds.

When Samba appealed to his father, he advised his son to become a sun worshipper (Vijaya Tunga, J.1963: 8). The Samba Purana narrates that although Samba could prove his innocence, the curse once uttered could not be taken back. The only possibility of mitigating this curse was through penance and propitiating the sun god. The cursed Samba retired to the Maitri forest on the Chandrabhaga River and underwent rigorous austerities. He abstained from food, subsisting on air alone, with mental faculties all under control and constantly meditating on Surya. Finally, Surya Deva was pleased. After twelve years of perfect devotion, the sun god took pity on him and appearing before him in visible form, offered to front him a boon. Samba asked for the blessings of remaining forever devoted to Surya. Still better pleased, the sun god allowed him one more boon. Samba requested Surya Deva to cure his disease. The grace of the sun god made Samba to recover his pristine beauty. The next morning while he bathed in the Chandrabhaga River, he found a stone image of Surya. The image conversed with him and asked him to build a temple for its worship. The magnificent temple was finished. Samba was perplexed to know not whom he should call to officiate the ceremony. The sun god himself asked him to fetch from Shakadvipa (Iran) some Magas, for the worship in this temple. This very settlement is recognized as the original place from which this type of sun worship spread all over India. This place was called Mulasthan or Sambapura. The later part of the Samba Purana transfers the erection of the first Surya sanctuary to the shores of the eastern ocean, into Tapovana, a forest inhabited by ascetics (Alice Boner: XXXV).

The Manus of the Tapovara seems to have discovered the image of the sun god. At sunrise, they found it immersed in the ocean doubling the appearance of the sun in the sky. They brought it ashore and it was Vaivasvata Manu built a temple for it. Vasistha related this story to Samba in order to show that the sanctuary on the salt ocean was of far greater antiquity than the one erected by Samba in Sambapurana. The Praci Mahatmya and the Kapila Samhita are the later Orissan texts. They identify Tapovana with the present site of Konarka, designated as Arkashetra or Surya Kshetra.

However, they still attribute to Samba for the erection of the temple. The Bhavishya, the Varaha and other Puranas when relating the story of Samba, say that he established three sanctuaries to the sun god. They were at Udayacala, Kalapriya near the Yamuna and at Sambapura. The icons consecrated was in benediction first to the rising sun, the second to the sun in the zenith and the third to the setting sun. The Brahma Purana chapter 28 also identifies the site of Konarka as a place of sun worship. The text goes on to describe the great festival of the sun god on the seventh day of the bright fortnight of Magha, when the devotee should purify himself by bathing in the ocean and should greet the rising sun with the Mantra of three syllabus Bhu, Bhuvan, Svar and with special offerings. It concludes by saying that who so ever makes this pilgrimage to the sun god with faith and self-control and sees the Vimana of red colour, the chariot of the sun god, arise from the ocean will finally reach the abode of Surya. In the Surya Tantra or Surya Tantra Vistara, there is another semi-historical account which confirms that the Maithraic form of sun worship migrated from the Northern regions to the South. It distinguishes two different branches of sun worshippers or Sauras.

People who dwelled in the Shaka Dvipa (Iran) were Arkins and the Maitrins dwelled at Jambu Dvipa (India) and are called Maitrins. Various places of pilgrimage consecrated to the two cults are also stated. Those of the Arkins are mostly in the Punjab and extend Southward to the Ganga and to Western India. Those of Maitris range from the Ganga eastward to the Praci river in Northern Orissa and the Chandrabhaga in the Maitri forest, The Konarka of today. The Southern branch, which still has many adherents in Orissa, are called the Sambika branch, because its followers worship Samba together with Surya (Alice Boner: 26).

Sources related to Upa Puranas and other stories of Samba (Kanwarlal 1967: 10), it appears that the prince Samba was a really ill-starred youth. Through his mad pranks, he not only brought trouble upon himself but also upon his relatives and was finally the cause of the total extinction of the race to which he belonged. He made fun of sacred things and led a desolate life. Once he and his companions' played a practical joke on the three sages Vishvamitra, Durvasa and Narada. Samba dressed himself as pregnant women and asked the sages whether it would be a boy or a girl. This was a great mockery and insult to the learned sages. The sages being angry cursed the son of Krishna that he would bring an iron club that shall destroy the race of Yadus. The same thus happened. The iron club was ordered to be smashed and thrown into the ocean. One piece of that iron entered into a fish. The fatal arrow prepared from the very iron piece unfortunately killed Krishna. The powdered portion of the iron club thrown in the sea produced rushes of waves. When plucked they turned into clubs or reeds that served as swords. All these weapons were inturn-wielded that in turn ended the race of the Yadus.

Another account attributes that, Bishnu Maharaj the master architect the one who designed and built the Konark edifice. He dedicated his life building temples. He left his home for many years living behind his newborn son, and his wife. His son also nurtured in his father's lines also grew up proficient in this art of building. The young architect was none other than Dharmapada. He went in search of his father engrossed in the building of temple. The legend says that there was a mistake in calculation at its final stage. There was a delay in the work, as the master could not place the Amalaka in its right position. The king became furious. The young son came to the rescue of his father and adjusting the calculation, finished the tower. The young boy caring for the prestige and reputation of his father committed suicide by drowning himself in the river Chandrabhaga (Gangoly, O.C. and Chowdhury. S 1956: 127).

The native villagers also believe and have a fable to account. They relate to the installation of the Kumbha Patra or load stone of immense size on the tower. Narrators believe that it had an effect of drawing ashore all vessels passing near the coast. The sailors felt inconvenient of this. About two century since, the times of Moghul's, the crew of the ship landed at the distance

and steering down the coast, attacked the temple, scaled the tower, and carried off the loadstone. The priests alarmed at the violation of the sanctity of the place removed the image of the god with all his paraphernalia to Puri where they have ever since remained and from that date. The temple without the Icon went into disuse and rapidly went into ruins (O.C. Ganguly, Chowdhury .S, 1956: 127). The origin of the dilapidation and destruction may also have been due to earthquake, lightning. Apart from the destruction by the weather conditions, vandalism by the inhabitants of the neighbourhood has accelerated the cause. They have forced out the iron clamps, which held the stones together for the sake of the metal. It is a well-known fact that the officers of the records narrate that the Marhatta government actually brought down a part of the wall, to procure materials for building some insignificant temples at Puri even while viewing into the historical facts from the core legends even with the historical figures. Credits bestow Narasinghan Deva-I as the illustrious ruler of the Ganga dynasty. Credit goes in his way for the construction of the great monument to his fame. The Raja himself suffered from leprosy. The Sun God had to be propitiated for cure. He got it cured by his dedication and devotion to the sun. This explains the reason for him to build the sun temple at Konark that too to a deity whose worship was not in vogue (Kanwarlal 1956: 13). However, there is no concrete evidence to prove this legend of a historical character. Almost all historians agree that Narasingha Deva –I was indeed the builder of this celebrated temple.

Bayacakada Manuscripts

The Bayacakada the largest of the manuscripts starts from the 5th Anka of Narasimha with the excavation for the foundation of the temple. It ends in the 18th Anka with the consecration of all shrines and their images. The accounts reveal that it took six years of preparatory work including drawing of the plan and quarrying of the stones. Workers recruited are not included however are supposedly deposited in the Jaganath Mandir, Puri.

The manuscript provides exact information about the methodology of work process. The organization of labour forces, providing valuable documentation on numerous technical matters such as the provenance of various building stories, the method used for quarrying and transporting them, the technique of lifting enormous stones to considerable height and the process of casting huge iron girdles used in the construction. Also revealed are the names not only of the leading artists but also of all other collaborators including even ordinary workers, registering their contracts. Truly, a unique work of its kind the records reveal their orders and their remuneration they received for each single piece of work. The most important name, which comes as an important reference, is of Sadashiva Samantaraya Mahapatra, who held the title of Sutradhara, the director and final authority on every point of the construction.

According to Bayacakada the work commenced on the temple towards the end of the 5th Anka of Narasimha's reign. It ended some 12 years 10 months and 14 days, later during his 18th Anka. Installation of the image of Mahabhaskara took place on Sunday the 7th day of the Maghashukla Paksha in A.D.1238. Ten years or even twelve years seems an incredibly short time for the construction of such a mammoth undertaking. Care for Constructional organization of technical process with utmost precision was the aim. There was an astonishingly clear foresight, with time never being lost between one stage of work and the next.

The Bayacakada mentions that Narasimha kept pressurizing the Sutradhara to increase the momentum of the work. He wanted the consecration on the Shukla Saptami the great festival of the sun god that would fall on a Sunday. On that auspicious day at sunrise, the king wanted the performance of the pooja to take place inside the temple.

The work stopped in the early years of construction, during the rainy season. The workers went to their hometowns. In the later years work continued throughout the monsoon period. In spite of

tremendous difficulties that crept in during the setting of the Kalasha on the top of the main temple, all of the consecration ceremonies completed in proper time. Thomas .E. Donaldson opines that this enforced haste in furnishing the work which have impaired the cohesion and strength of the upper parts of the temple.

According to the manuscript, the installation of a large Gaja simha on the eastern façade took place. Hasty Closing of the first ceiling was at the instance of the king and against the wishes of the Sutradhara. Symptoms of instability became evident with the setting of the Beki stone on the roof of the Gandi. The stone of the Beki was twice rest and finally consolidated with metal clamps. Still worse difficulties arose later. The Sutradhara had the greatest challenge before him where he had to abandon the attempt to set the Kalasha on top of the Khapura crowning the Amalaka. Dharmamahapatra saved the situation by making a new Kalasha. With the aid of a supporting pedestal, the Kalasha got fixed in the Khapura. Boner implies that, this suggests that some thing had gone wrong with the under structure, perhaps it had not been made solid enough or had not been made allowed sufficient time to settle properly and in its own balance. Further evidence of this is implied by the act of plastering over the uppermost part of the Gandi (Thomas.E.Donaldson,1996: 594 -595).

Abul Fazil in his work mentioned above has given great tribute to the monument. Declaring that, even those whose judgment is critical and who are difficult to be pleased, be astonished by its sight. He also mentions six other sites within the enclosure and twenty-two others in the vicinity, which further suggests that the whole temple was still intact in situ (H.S. Jarrett and Jadu-Nath Sarkar, 1949: 140-141). This statement contradicts the popular tradition recorded in the Madala Panji (Fascid no.7 of Mukunda Deva). It states that the temples were damaged and desecrated during the invasion of Orissa in 1568 by the Muslims of Bengal under Kalapahada (Madala Panji, Prachi edition 1940.: 60-62). The temple was still in worship even in the early 17th century. This is confirmed by another entry in the Madala Panji, Fascicle no.3 of Purushottamadeva of the Khurda dynasty (A.D. 1607-1621) recording a survey of the temple along with the Lingaraja and the Jagannatha and a report on the expenditures for the worship and on the contents on their store room and treasuries. It is in later recordings and entry of Fascicle no.6 of Raja Narasimha Deva (A.D. 1621-1647) that narrates the catastrophes' leading to the eventual collapse of the Gandi. It is at this time, during the 9th Anka of his reign (A.D. 1628) that the colossal Gaja-simha of the eastern façade fell, crumbling the eastern wall under its weight and breaking the hands of the Puja image.

The description of the Gandi with the fall of the projecting Gaja-Simha rather by an enemy attack appears substantiated by the fact that the southern and western walls remained upright to a height of 150 ft at least until 1837 A.D., as confirmed by Fergusson and a drawing made at that time (James Fergusson 1848:27-28).

Raja Narasimha Deva- I. The Builder

Local tradition attributes the name Narasingha Deva to Raja Narasimha Deva-I. Records in Madala Panji (Fascicle 7), of the Keshari dynasty states that in 9th cen. CE., Purandhara Keshari, king of Orissa was a great devotee of the sun god. He prayed and did Puja to Amshumalin in the Konarka Kshetra. Along with the construction of a tall temple at the Kshetra, it had eight Brahmanas kept in eight villages in benediction to the sun god. The Baya Chakada also contains evidence that the cult of the sun god in the Arkashetra was anterior to the erection of the big temple by Narasimha Deva. On completion of the new temple, immersion of the old image of Surya with worn out features took place in the ocean. The Ganga dynasty under Ananthavarman Codaganga had superseded the Somavamshi Kesari dynasty in the early 12th century invading Orissa from the Deccan. Anangabhima –II one of his successors, consolidated Ganga power in the early 13th

century CE. The Madala Panji records that Narasimha Deva-I was the son of Anangabhima – II (table 1). At the very young age of eighteen, the prince had to fight in the south for three years as the commander-in-chief of his father’s army. From this campaign, he brought home a huge booty. On the advice of his mother, he had to build a Parama Deula for the sun god. The records also say that there was Ekamara Deula (Lingaraja temple), in Sankhakshetra, Purushottama (Jagannatha temple) in Puri), in the Gada Kshetra and Viraja (Devi temple in jajpur)(Alice Boner 1972: XXVIII-XXXII).

Genealogy of the Imperial Ganga

Table 1 Genealogy of the Imperial Ganga

As stated earlier the building operations started in the fifth Anka of Narasimha Deva. Preparations planning and quarrying of stones had already begun six years earlier. The work had started on the project when Narasimha was still a crown prince. Narasimha a great warrior and powerful ruler not only repulsed all attacks of the Muslims from the south and the north but also re-conquered the territories occupied by them in the Gauda Desha (Bengal). In 1243-1245 CE, he inflicted a crushing defeat on the Nawab’s of Bengal, who were supported by the Muslim emperors of Delhi.

In consequence of his victories, Orissa experienced relative peace for another three hundred years and he could preserve its indigenous culture. Muslims occupied Orissa in 1568 CE.

The work Ekavali dealing with Alankara, by the poet Vidyadhara sings in praise of Narasimha in 314 verses. The poem is still a controversy among scholars in Orissa. Some also ascribe it to Narasimha –III. Alice Boner (Alice boner 1972: XXXX) opines that sculptural testimony and from an entry in Madala Panji that, the work is attributed to Narasimha-I. The king is praised as great warrior and heroes because he inflicted a major defeat on the Muslim invaders from Bengal. This prolonged the war.

The war started in 1213 CE. Under Anangabhima-II, ended in about 1245 CE. With Narasimha's conquest of Radha and Varendri, two districts of Bengal. The copper plate grants of Narasimha-II and Narasimha-IV of Ganga dynasty has recovered this. It is also mentioned in Baya Cakada (leaf VIII, 23 and leaf XXXV, 9) where details are given of the booty brought home the use that was made of it in furthering the work of the temple.

The Ekavali earned the Raja the glory of reincarnation of Vishnu's Narasimha Avatara. He was the only Orissan Maharaja who fought against the aggression of the Muslims of Bengal.

The Ekavali calls him as Yavanavani Vallabha (lord of the land of the Yavanas, meaning foreigners, Muslims).

The Ekavali praises the Raja with the title Shilpajna (knower of Silpas. He gets this title by his magnificent building activities. Records speak that he kept his own agents in the Purushottama temple to spot any scholar coming for Darshan. In the due course of making the Konark temple (Figure 1), these scholars received invitation for their advice and opinion. Narasimha Deva took great precautions in building the temple according to proper rules. From the very beginning, he established a settlement of Pandits, knower of Shilpa Shastras near the temple for ready consultation.

Discussion

Thus, from the above, we understand that in South Asian context for any good cause to happen the whole event is surrounded by the concept of divine origin. The whole event involves, the divine place (Kshetra) involving the celestial deities and the Rajan, the Pratyaksha devata. Every event encapsulated in a divine garb, has a core message to communicate to the world. In this case, it is through legends, the message of medico connection with the belief that the light of the sun is a cure for leprosy is communicated. It indicates that, the ancient cognizance is trying to highlight the importance of Sun's rays as treatment for skin disorders. For this purpose at the metaphysical level, the energy of the Sun's rays through the powers of the Sun God, the Sun God himself being made the pinnacle and centre of attention, through whom the understanding of the medical remedies relating to the healing nature of the Sun's rays is propagated. At the second level, the Raja himself considered as Pratyakshadevata, takes a lead in the construction of the temple. Here too myths and legends encircle him that leads him to unfold, the construction of the magnificent Konark Surya Devula (Figure 1).

The deeper message is that, the people of all walks of life, scholarly to common, including the king, were engaged in searching for a remedy for the treatment of Leprosy which might have been a common and rampant disease (skin disorder) in the Orissan belt in India.

Thus, the myths and legends play an important role in not only communicating a story but to understand the contemporary needs and immediate remedies to be sorted out for a better living.

Figure 1: Surya Devula, Konark

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Prof. Ravi Mohanty, Deccan College, Post -Graduate and Research Institute, for all his encouragement and guidance to work on Konark Surya Devula. Sincere thanks to University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for extending financial aid as part of UGC Minor Research Project for the current topic discussed above.

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